

MODERN METHODS OF FOREIGN LANGUAGE TEACHING

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Annotation. This article is about the methodology of foreign language teaching, as the subject history of development modern method used in foreign language teaching methodology types and their use.

Keyword: methodology, foreign language, innovation, communication, skills, competencies, didactics, intercultural communication.

Introduction. Modern educational development has given rise to a new direction of innovative pedagogy. Innovative - means "introduction (dissemination) of innovation" in English. The socio - psychological aspect of innovation was developed by the American researcher E. Rodiers. It is an innovation process studied the classification of participants, their attitude to the news, etc. The concepts of novelty and innovation are mutually different in scientific areas "Innovation" means a tool, new method, methodology, technology, "Innovation" is a process that develops according to certain stages of education. The development of world science is growing and developing day by day. It was this positive development that effected our country as well. Advanced innovative technologies are being applied to our world of science. As a result of this, our President named this year as " Year of Youth Support and Public Healths", which increased the responsibility of the youth of our country. It would not be wrong to say that the wide application of advanced, modern innovative technologies in the fields of education has opened the door to many opportunities and goals for young people learning foreign languages.

Language learning is one of the most important areas in human society. Language which is a means of communication, can be acquired practically in a natural environment, i.e. in the family, in the community or in an organized manner. Knowledge of language phenomena is taught theoretically. Knowledge of languages, especially multilingualism is of great importance in our time of increased international relations. Pupils and students studying in our country usually study three languages. These languages are referred to by special names. These are mother tongue, second language, and foreign language. The mother tongue is the first language that plays a special role in the formation of thinking. When talking about the second language, it is considered as the language of brothers and neighbors of other nationalities. A foreign language is the language

of a foreign country. Western European languages (English, Spanish, German, French) and Eastern languages (Arabic, Turkish, Persian, Chinese, Indian) are taught in our republic. These languages are included in the curricula of educational institutions. The process of teaching all three languages is different. The mother tongue and the second language are learned in a natural situation, and a foreign language is learned in an artificial environment. Communication in a foreign language mainly takes place in the classroom under the guidance of the teacher. Among the three languages, learning and teaching a foreign language differs sharply in certain aspects. This, in turn, requires the use of appropriate foreign language teaching technology. By carefully mastering the achievements of the methodical science, the foreign language teacher will be able to clearly know the standard of language experience of the student and to improve it further. Effective teaching of foreign languages requires knowledge of its methodology. Learning and teaching foreign languages in many ways involves the issues of foreign language teaching methodology from a theoretical point of view.

The history of methods is the famous methodist prof. Deeply studied by I.V. Rakhmonov. The method of translation is mainly in two forms, called grammar translation and text translation methods. From the point of view of the grammar translation method, a foreign language is studied for general educational purposes. Grammatical exercises are performed in order to develop the logical thinking of the language learner. Expressing grammatical knowledge is considered the main goal of education. The main principles of these methods are as follows:

1. Language learning is based on written speech.
2. Grammar was taken as the subject of study, lexis was chosen according to it, grammar exercises were the main method of work.
3. First, grammatical rules were memorized, and then it was recommended to make sentences based on the rules.
4. Grammatical forms and the meaning of words in the means of literal translation revealed.
5. Language material is mastered by literal translation and dry memorization.
6. Limited to individual memorization of words out of context.

The new interpretation of the purpose of foreign language education was mainly based on the results of pragmatic linguistic research. This branch of linguistics interprets language not as a system of linguistic forms, but as a field of human activity. In the field of foreign language education, since the beginning

of the 70s, a set of new conclusions had led to intense discussions in the field of educational goal setting. In the 70s, the "communicative method" was proven in several stages after a series of attempts. In this way, the science of methodology was developing. We cannot master any foreign language without a deep study of its methodology. The method "communicative didactics" is also considered important in the methodology of foreign language teaching. Communicative didactics includes the following:

- open and flexible lesson concepts;
- subject and content are important;
- the main form of work in the lesson: talking and working in groups;
- students to activate and use the language creatively and feely attention must be great;
- strong training based on principle of understanding to express thoughts pay attention to;
- Visualization (visual support) plays in important role in revealing the meaning, defining the scope of action and organizing the exercise;
- studying daily speech communication in a real life situation (practice dialogue do);
- it is important to use the language orally and at the same time to understand the original texts.

Conclusion: Learn a foreign language is a multifaceted discipline, in which a person undergoes complex psychological changes. In particular, the process of comparing the native language with a foreign language occurs. Various teaching methods and technologies are used in this process. With the help of modern pedagogical technologies, teaching by comparing the foreign language with the mother tongue gives an effective results. Teaching a foreign language requires knowledge of its methodology. Methodology and technologies are important in the process of learning a foreign language. There are various methods of teaching methodology. The widely used methods in foreign language teaching methodology are: communicative didactic method, intercultural dialogue organization method and exercise organization method. All three methods are closely related and complement each other. Since the science of methodology is related to the science of didactics, it is based on communicativeness during foreign language learning and the method of communicative didactics is created.

Practice is the best way to master all knowledge. The exercise gives a positive result not only in foreign language education, but also in the acquisition of knowledge in all fields. Effective organization of the lesson, the role of the

pedagogue and modern pedagogical technologies in it is incomparable. It is important to organize the process of learning a foreign language with a communicative approach, to bring the next level to the level of intercultural communication, and to achieve such results, it is important to pay attention to the last step, "exercise technology". In order to effectively organize the process of teaching a foreign language, it is necessary to acquire knowledge of modern pedagogical information and communication technologies.

References:

1. Makhmudov, Q, S, O, G, L, Shaikhislamov, N. Z. O. G. L. & Joe, B. O. G. L.(2020). Description, place and classification of antonyms in Uzbek and foreign languages. Science and Education, 1(special issue 3).
2. Juraboyev, B. B. O.(2020). Communicative approach to teaching German. Science and Education, 7(7), 215-220.
3. Samarova, S. (2018). Forming Creative Vision of Person as Universal Method Enhancing Creativity. Eastern European Scientific Journal, (6).
4. Samarova, S. R. (2019). Methods and technologies for the development of creative thinking of pupils. European Journal of Research and Reflection in Educational Sciences, 7(10), 37-43.
5. Zaraboyev, B. O. (2021). Using authentic materials on English lessons. Academic research in educational sciences, 2(2).
6. Juraboyev, B.B.U. (2021). Problems and solutions for online teaching and learning a foreign languages. Academic research in educational sciences. 2(special issue 2).
7. Samarova, S. R, & Mirzayeva, M. M.(2020). The problem of the formation of creative abilities of students in foreign psychology. An international Multidisciplinary Research Journal, 10(5). 1937-1943.
8. Rakhmanova, M. K. (2019). Old Middle School in the spiritual education of young people importance of Asian spiritual and cultural heritage. "Spiritual and educational technologies of patriotic education in the consitions of globalization" republican scientific - practical conference, 206-209.
9. Rakhmanova, M. K. (2019). Theoretical and methodological foundations of the development of social activity in students. Public education, (1), 24-29.

